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Leveraging National Philosophy of Education through Value Re-Orientation among Secondary School Students in Nigeria: A Philosophical Approach

Nkaanee, Samuel Nneebea¹
Samuelnkaanee@gmail.com

Brown Isioma Rosemary¹

¹Department of Educational Foundations, River State University, River State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined the leverage on National philosophy of education through value re-orientation among secondary school students in Nigeria using a philosophical approach. This study has been considered necessary because education is the pivotal force of growth and development in any given nation. The study employed philosophical method which entails prescribing, analyzing and speculating the need for a good educational value re-orientation in the Nigerian society. The insights gleaned from the study is that philosophy of education is based on full integration of the individual community. Similarly, the finding showed that the aim of the national policy on education in Nigeria with quite a number of value orientation statements as enshrined in the policy objectives are defeated as it affects the problem of implementation. It is also discovered that the aim of education has not answered what constitute the right type of values and society it has proposed. The study recommends that youths who are leaders of tomorrow should shun sharp practices or evil, but rather invest such time in acquiring sound education.

Keywords: Education, values re-orientation, society,

Introduction

Education is an indispensable tool for human development in the cognitive, affective, psycho-motive and psycho-productive domains. It is imperative to note that society cannot grow or develop without recourse to educational system, be it formal, informal, and non-formal. Every average individual pass through all of these knowingly or unknowingly. Amaele, Jerome & Abee (2011:5) maintains that education “involves a desirable change in human behaviour through the process of teaching and learning”. This underscores the fact that teaching and learning are as old as human’s existence. It follows that any human being who does not exhibit desirable behaviours from the point of view of the acceptable societal norms and values cannot be adjudged an educated person, even if he had passed through the four walls of an educational institution. A person’s behaviour determines the level of his education. This behaviour according to Amaele, et al, (2011) must conform to the desirable behaviour acceptable to the societal norms. Education therefore should produce a well cultured and meaningful person in- the society. Ijah (2010:50) equates education with light and illiteracy with darkness. Education to him, therefore, is a process of instilling and sharpening or modifying the attitudes, habits and behaviours of the individual for proper adjustment in the society. The level of ones’ education determines the extent of his development.

The purpose of this study is to focus on the role of educational values in Nigerian nation’s philosophy as it reflect in our societal norms and values. From the fore-going, our value system as enshrined in the National Policy on education has been relegated to the background. Values refer to the quality of being useful or important. It can also be seen as a belief in what is right and wrong and what is important in life (Hornby, 2009). In a more dimensional form, values are dispositions, beliefs and behaviours that are very useful by a particular society. Amaele (2007) sees values as standards of conduct, efficiency or worth which a society endorses, maintains and even transmits to her members in present and future generations. Therefore, it behoves that the very essential ingredients in the lives of individuals and nation is their value system. The lives of an individual, community and nation is sharpened and determined by value system which is in line with their national philosophy. The quality or nature of such nation’s philosophy depicts the lives of the citizens.

Consequently, the Lack of proper educational values system has informed this work. The gap so far created needs to be filled for Nigerians to have a well cultured and valued educational system that will usher in a corrupt-free society. It has been a serious concern seeing our economic crumbling and poverty raiding quarters because of ineffective value system in the society. Lack of proper educational values system has informed this

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work. The gap so far created needs to be filled for Nigerians to have a well cultured and valued educational system that will usher in a corrupt-free society. It has been a serious concern seeing our economic crumbling and poverty raiding quarters because of ineffective value system in the society. A number of definitions have been proposed for the term 'education' by both sociologists and philosophers of education. However, etymologically, 'education' derives from the Latin word 'educere' meaning to lead out or pull out (Elechi and Ogbondah, 2006). Plato and other idealists believe that a given learner has some innate potentialities, which need to be squeezed out, pulled out, and expanded (Osaat, 2012). John Locke, a realist views 'education' as having its origin from the Latin word 'educare' meaning to train. In the view of John Locke, a learner's mind needs training and filling with information and knowledge.

According to Ifeanacho (1998) education is the most recognized method by which a person acquires most of his ideas, beliefs, attitudes, skills and manners necessary not only to combat the hazards and problems of life, and to re-occurs the needs of life but also to fit into the company of humans. Enoh et al (1987) defines education as the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develops the abilities, attitudes, and other forms of behaviour which are of positive value to the society in which he/she lives. Emile Durkheim, in Okoh (2004), sees education as the systematic socialization of the younger generation by which the latter learns religions and moral beliefs, feelings of nationality and collective opinions of all kinds. The Advanced learner's Dictionary of current English (2005) defines education as the systematic training and instruction designed to impact knowledge and develop skills.

Agabi and Okorosaye-Orubite (2005) see education as the process of acquiring knowledge and ideas that shape and condition man's attitudes, actions and achievements. Ukeje adds that education in the process of developing the child's moral, physical, emotional and intellectual powers for his contribution in social reform and the mastery of the laws of nature and their effective use for the welfare of members of the society. Hirst (1979) believe that educating people suggests a family of processes whose principle of unity is the development of desirable qualities in them. There desirable qualities are the values of the society.

Methodology

This study adopted a philosophical approach which entails; prescriptive, speculative and analytical processes. The data used for this study was gotten from both primary and secondary sources of information. Education has been defined as a concept, though with difficulties to apprehend. Yet, its puzzles cannot completely wipe, out the meaning of the concept. The questions that bordered so much on scholars' mind is whether there is a Nigerian Education and if there is, what are its characteristics? (Amaele, 2010). This question does not undermine the fact that there existed educational system in Nigeria before the western oriented education which many critics mistake for a formal educational system in the country. Their argument depicts that it has no roots as well not embedded in, the existing culture of the indigenous society. However, we could not dismiss the argument completely because some features of western education are enshrined in the indigenous education. For clarification, we have about four Nigerian educational systems. This includes (a) the indigenous or traditional system of education (b) Islamic education (c) Western education and finally (d) Modern education.

The indigenous or traditional system of education is the transmission of skills, culture and knowledge orally from one generation to another. Amaele (2010) opined that it is the acculturation of the individual members of the community to acquire the necessary skills and wisdom to survive in the environment without foreign interference, while passing same from one generation to another. Okujagu and Wokocha (1999) view it as the education handed down to succeeding generations quite apart from the western style of education of the school system or the formal education of the koranic schools. The system does not have any particular place to learn or thought, rather it is done at any place, anywhere and anytime. The elders are teachers.

The Islamic Education is basically traceable to the Muslim of Northern Nigeria. The aim is to produce people that are specialists in the tenant of Islam. Wokocha and Okujagu (1999) postulate that its aim to turn out or prepare the children for adult life as Muslims, not just as a religion but to adopt it as a way of life. Muslims are always commanded to pursue and seek knowledge wherever knowledge is found. Islamic schools were established, blossomed and grew into large centres of high learning. Okoli, (2011) also views the aim of Islamic education as that which is based on religious education as the foundation of moral conduct and practical living. Just like the indigenous traditional education, Islamic education also aims at, the transmission of Islamic culture and maintains individual self-consciousness within the Islamic community. Their educational style is rooted in the Quran and the teaching and practices of their Noble prophet, Mohammed (Peace be Upon Him). Islamic education gained entrance into Northern part of Nigeria through Islamic traders from the Sahara Desert into Bornu

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and Hausa States in the 14th and 15th centuries (Okoli 2011). By the 19th century Usman Dan Fodio carried out his Jihad amongst the Hausa states in order to correct the ills and darts and to root out elements of ant-Islamic practice.

The Nigerian education today is an offshoot of Western education. It began with the missionary activities in the 16th century. Amaele observes that an earlier attempt to establish the faith and its education in Nigeria failed. The 19th century Missionaries of various Christian denominations arrived with a lasting introduction of Western formal education into Nigerian, which was later successful. However Islamic culture preceded that of its Western counterpart in Nigeria, but the latter has greater impact on the present Nigeria education. In fact, the indigenous and Islamic religions had already unique system of education. The interference of Christianity as a religion with education failed because they failed to study the cosmological foundations of the indigenous people (Amaele, 2010). They later regroup and began to send out another batch of missionaries that were result oriented. Such includes Mr & Mrs William de craft and Rev Thomas Birch Freeman in 1842 under the auspices of the Wesleyan Methodist Mission who arrived at Badagry and planted the first school. Rev Hope Waddel in 1946 who arrived Calabar established the Presbyterian Church Scotland Mission. Rev Ajayi Crowther and Rev S.C. Taylor in 1957 established Church Missionary work. Rev Fr. Joseph Shanahan arrived in Lagos and then Onitsha and established the Roman Catholic Mission (RCM). Rev. Thomas Bowen who arrived Ogbomosho for Missionary work (Okoli, 2011:60) and many others. All of them established schools which was basically formal education in Nigeria and was purely a Christian Missionary enterprise.

The Modern Education has an aspect of oral transmission just like the indigenous education. The teacher discusses, demonstrates and tries to practicalize topics and points. Okoli points out one of the aims of modern education as that which strives to enable the individual to be suitably and effectively fitted into society. She maintains that another aim of modern education is borrowed from indigenous educational scheme. It seeks to acquaint the child with modern ways of living successfully in the society. The modern education is predominantly invoked in the Nigerian educational system to day which will be discussed in the next topic. Modern education, therefore, has some inherent features of indigenous, Islamic and western education which serves as its bedrock.

Secondary School System of Education in Nigeria: Nigerian educational system is that given and obtained in the geographical entity called Nigeria. It is the educational system we received from the British government during the colonial period which ended on October 1, 1960. The Nigerian educational system comprises of the primary secondary and tertiary institutions of learning or schools. The primary school lasts for six years. Pupils are introduced to literacy and numeracy skills, morality, citizenship education, manipulative skills, ability to adapt to the environment and communicative skills. They learn arithmetic, verbal and quantitative reasoning, social studies, religious knowledge, basic science, music, history, fine creative arts, physical education, mathematics and cultural arts.

Originally, the secondary school lasted for five years. Students learnt mathematics, English language, fine Art, literature in English, Technical Drawing, Home Economic Business studies, Shorthand, Christian Religious Knowledge, French, Integrated science, music, etc up to form II. In form III, they learnt Geography, History, Physics, and Biology, chemistry, additional mathematics (now further mathematics), Economics, home management / foods and nutrition. In form IV students chose 8 subjects which they would sit for in the West African School Certificate/General Certificate of Education Examination held in May-June and October-November for school and private candidates respectively. Successful candidates then proceeded to Sixth Form, which lasted for two years (Lower Sixth Form and Upper Sixth Form). At this level, students were prepared for the Higher school certificate (HSC) and General Certificate of Education (Advanced level) in both science and art subjects. For instance, we had such combinations as physics/chemistry/Biology; physics/chemistry/mathematics; physics/Geography/mathematics; Religious knowledge/History/ Economics; History/Economics/Geography; Mathematics/Geography/Economics, etc. Successful candidates were admitted by Direct Entry mode of study leading to the award of a degree.

With the introduction of the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1987/88 session, the secondary school duration increased to six years. It was divided into junior secondary school and senior secondary school, each lasting three (3) years. Vocational subjects were introduced in the junior secondary section. There are introductory Technology, Electronics, mechanics, Building Technology, commentary and Joinery, computer Education, woodwork, etc. At the senior secondary level, students offer physics, chemistry, biology, economics, geography, history, further mathematics, mechanical and building drawing Nigerian language agricultural science, literature in English, music, French, English language, general mathematics, civics education, marketing, salesmanship, foods and nutrition/home management, etc. Candidates who succeed at the WAEC or NECO senior School Certificate Examination enter the university, polytechnic or college of Education through the University Joint

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matriculation and Admission matriculation Examination (UTME). In fact, the secondary school prepares us for useful life within the society and for higher education (NPE, 1981, 2004). Again, secondary education dictates the pace of learning at the primary and tertiary levels (Orake, 2004).

Tertiary education is the one received at the polytechnics, colleges of Education, schools of Health and Technology schools and Nursing, universities, research institutes and other related schools. Jaja (2013) views higher education as the Western type of education which is organized after college of Education. She adds that there are rules and regulations formulated and administered by the ministries of education to guide the type of building facilities, equipment and entry requirements. Idogho (2011) sees higher education is that which develops individuals mentally, morally and physically and to confer degrees on their products who are fund worthy in character and learning, to enable them assume leadership roles in their immediate and extended societies. The federal government of Nigeria (2004) sees higher education as that which provides quality education for her products so that they can assume leadership positions in their immediate and external communities.

The Nigerian Society

According to Spencer and Inkeles (1985), society is a group with a culture organized for the satisfaction of all human needs and 'interests. They add that the society consists of the people; their culture is what they have, what they do, and how they think together, culture is a way of life shared by a group, a system of ideas, beliefs, values, knowledge, and customs transmitted from one generation to another (Spencer and Inkeles, 1985:53). It is produced by a society; in turn, a society depends in its culture. There can be no culture without society and vice versa. The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary of Current English (2015) defines society as people in general living in communities. Secondly, it is a particular community of people who share the same customs, laws, etc. Thirdly, it is a group of people who join together for a particular purpose. Finally, it is a group of people in a country who are fashionable, rich and powerful.

Role of Educational Values in Nigeria National Philosophy of Education

Before examining the role of educational values in the Nigeria National philosophy of Education, let us first conceptualize the key words; role, morality, values and philosophy of education. Let us then take them one after the other. Sociologically, role is defined as the dynamic aspect of one's states, the way one acts out one's status. A role is defined in connection with other complementary roles. For example, the role of a teacher complements that of a pupil in the same way that of a patient complement that of a doctor, and so on (Spencer & Inkeles, 1985). The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary of current English (2015) defines role as the function or position that somebody has or is expected to have in an organization.

Morality is the group of principles concerning right and wrong or good and bad behaviour. It is also defined as the degree to which something is good or bad, right or wrong. The term 'morality derives from the adjective 'moral' which is used to modify something concerning wrong or right behavior (opp cited). Then, "Values" are beliefs about what is wrong or right. This is why we have moral values in our society to guide our behaviours. Both morality and values are to be considered in the National Philosophy of Education for any country. This is because educational philosophy must be based on the needs of members of the society with respect to social, political, economic moral and cultural development. This is to say that every philosophy of education must aim at national development and the sustainability of its educational system. For example, the philosophy of education for the United States depends on pragmatism while that of the United Kingdom is based on idealism (Osaat, 2010).

The National Philosophy of Education in Nigeria as formulated by the Federal Government of Nigeria (2004: 32) has the following objectives;

1. The building of a free and democratic society
2. The building of a just and egalitarian society
3. The building of a united, strong and self-reliant nation
4. The building of a great and dynamic economy
5. The building of a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens.

Based on the objectives of the Nigeria National Philosophy of Education, the quality of instruction at all levels of education should be geared towards the instilling of the following values;

1. Respect for the worth and dignity of individuals
2. Faith in man's ability to make rational decisions, moral and spiritual values in inter-personal and human elations

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3. Shared responsibility for the common good of the society.
4. Respect for the dignity of labour
5. And the promotion of emotional physical and psychological health of all children. (Osaat, 2010).

Certainly, certain things are not included in the sufficiency and relevance of the Nigerian philosophy of Education. There are no clarity of concepts and statement of aim, goals and objectives; ineffective implementation of the stated objectives, and the provision of guidance to the citizens and value system in the country. The concepts are not clear and the implementation is almost impossible. Again, the purpose of inculcation of moral values is defeated in this era of cultism, militancy, terrorism, human rights violation, high level of corruption, violation of distributive justice and absence of a just and egalitarian society. Aminigo (1999), in Nsirim believe that:

Moral education develops and sustains in the child interest and good attitude to morality, understand public morality, promotion of the understanding and commitment to intellectual norms and ability to make sound and independent moral judgment and the promotion of morality or behaviour.

Again, Ogbondah (2006), claims that all schools must reflect and encourage the acceptance of the argument on moral practices and values that are indispensable for the human quality of life in our society. According to him, the core values of social morality include honesty, truth, cooperation, respect for others, etc. He adds that moral education can be achieved through religion, literature, history, music, social studies, games, civics, etc. Again, he affirms that ethical or moral teaching focuses on authority, tolerance, sportsmanship, charity, duty, honesty, standards, right and wrong, etc. Elechi and Ogbondah (2006) also believe that a functional education must be based on morality and the relationship between members of the society. Accordingly, Uriah says the following with respect to moral education in our school curriculum:

A functional education must have moral values which reflect human relationship, that is, man's conduct towards other men. The examples of moral values are honesty, brotherhood, neighborliness, justice, equity and freedom; (Uriah in Elechi&Ogbondah, 2006:48).

Anikpo (2005:19) writing about value system and its effects on Nigerian education system reports that:

Our universities can no longer guarantee that necessary peace of mind for the student in her hall, the researcher in the library, the scientist in the laboratory, the philosopher under the tree. Nowhere in our once serene campus can poets now afford to stand and share. And this, the epidemic noise of nonsense, the loud crusades of evangelical groups who have turned students' hostels, classrooms, staff quarters, and virtually every open space on campus into screaming area for revivals and miracles.

From the above assertion, Osundare believes that the idea of morality has clipped us in the Nigeria university campuses since laws of morality are neglected and negated by fellow members of the education system.

Osaat and Omordu (2011) argue that "the Nigerian education system has suffered a lot of setbacks as a result of immorality. This is because, according to them, the high rate of immorality has affected the country's education in the following ways:

In the universal primary education scheme for which the sum of N636.03 million was allocated for the construction of 150,955 classrooms during the 1975.80 third National Development plan, only 63,000 classrooms were completed and yet, an additional N120,000,000 was incurred at the end of the plan period (political Bureau Report, 1989:66).

Value System and Value Re-orientation

Philosophy of Education is relevant or necessary in national value re-orientation. This is so because education is noted for the preparations of the citizens for meaningful existence and development. Values determined the intellectual norms and identity of a society. Value therefore is defined as those objects which human beings cherish, appreciate, want, desire or need as to achieve the goal of healthy living in pursuit of happiness (Isichei, 2000). To the psychologists, values are desirable which influence selective behaviour independent of specific situations (Francis Isichei & Stephen Bolaji, 2010). They maintain that value is something that a person prizes and cherishes, something that someone chooses freely from alternative after considering the consequences of those alternatives and causes a person to act or refrain from acting. Values are dynamic according to its peculiarities. Human life begins from childhoods to adolescents where ideals and values are acquired with a unique educational period with the enhancement of a more relevance stand of philosophy of education in value system.

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Society cannot exist without the principles or norms for moral behaviours which are values. In the life of humans, there are ideal of what is right and wrong in quest to pursuit happiness as values. Therefore, whenever the ethical norms are considered as a major objective of education, then we have a philosophy of education for moral behaviour. To this extent, education seems to be moral because the end result of all teachings is to complete the moral growth of a child and impart into the child the moral ideas of the society or nation. Schools cannot be value- free, whereas every nation must have it ethical norms with a share set of values to guide her children adapt to what they have been taught in schools or in the society. Such includes honesty, truthfulness, peace, love, freedom, tolerance, respect, cooperation, happiness etc. Children develop in morals and intellectual lives. This is in tandem with Nigerians as stipulated in her national policy on education (2014) on all levels of Nigeria educational system to be oriented towards inculcating the values into the lives of her citizens.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study showed that it is imperative that moral values be contained in a country's philosophy of Education. Right from Antiquity, philosophers of education ensured that moral education was incorporated into the curriculum of primary and secondary schools. As a result, the Nigeria National philosophy on Education aims at building (1) a free and democratic society, (2) a just and egalitarian state, (3) a united, strong and reliable nation, (4) a great and dynamic economy, and (5) a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens. Based on the above national goals the National policy on Education aims to instil the following educational values into the children:

1. Respect for the worth and dignity of individuals
2. Faith in man's ability to make rational decisions, moral and spiritual values in interpersonal and human relations.
3. Shared responsibility for the common good of the society.
4. Respect for the dignity of labour and the promotion of the emotional, physical and psychological growth of children.

The study further revealed that value plays a vital role in human life and this depends on the importance that is attached to it. Values are conducts, life styles, beliefs, dispositions, etc that people of a particular society cherished. This implies that not every valued life system is universal or applicable to all societies in the world. What is good or wrong in one society might not be so in the other society. However, by implication and importance educational values seem to be universal. Therefore, the quality or nature of the nation's philosophy is directed to the quality of life of her citizens which Nigeria is no exception.

The finding also reveals that the National Policy on Education in Nigeria had provided series of number of value-oriented statements enshrined in the first section of the policy. This policy sets certain objectives for the nation (Nigeria) and the nation's education such as;

1. Development of the individual into morally sound patriotic and effective citizens
2. Total integration of the individual into the immediate community, the Nigeria society and the world
3. Provision of equal access to qualitative educational opportunities for all citizens at all levels within and outside, the formal school system
4. Inculcation of national consciousness, values and national unity.

Development of appropriate skills, mental physical and social abilities and competences to empower the society (FRN, 2004.4).

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends the following:

- i. Educationists should take up the responsibility of providing pure and true knowledge to the youth as they live exemplary lives worthy of emulations.
- ii. Every profession comes with an ethics and the youth must not only keep the ethics but also influence the society to build a life oriented towards values and ethics.

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